

D6.1: Identifying & selection of use cases on good practices in XR

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ABSTRACT:	This deliverable report presents findings from a survey exploring good practices and use cases for XR technologies. Experts identified several applications such as training, education, entertainment, and healthcare, emphasizing the importance of user experience, technology, and overall goals. However, they noted that current XR systems are largely inaccessible to individuals with vision loss, low stereoacuity, poor digital literacy, and motor or cognitive impairments. The results will inform a Delphi study for consensus on best practices and guide the development of an online platform and demonstrator sites across Europe.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the findings from an exploratory survey aimed at identifying use cases and examples of good practice in XR. We invited experts working with XR technologies to participate in the survey and analysed their responses. The survey highlighted several use cases for XR, including training and education, entertainment, and healthcare. The experts we surveyed also shared several examples of good practices in XR, such as using immersive experiences to improve patient outcomes in healthcare and using XR to create engaging and interactive learning and training experiences. Our analysis of the survey responses revealed that the effective use of XR requires careful consideration of factors such as the user experience, the technology used, and the overall goals of the application. We also asked our experts to rate the extent to which current technologies were accessible for a broad range of demographics. Their responses revealed that current systems are almost fully inaccessible for individuals with full or nearly full vision loss and noted accessibility issues for individuals with low stereoacuity, poor digital literacy and people with motor and cognitive impairments. Overall, these experts felt that current XR technologies were only accessible to approximately half of society. The outcomes from this deliverable will be used to inform a Delphi study, where we will consult a selection of our expert respondents to reach a consensus on best practices. Moving forward, these identified use cases and examples of good practice will serve as important guides as we develop a library of experiences to showcase on our planned online platform and demonstrator sites across Europe.

1 INTRODUCTION

Extended Reality (XR), an umbrella term encompassing Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Mixed Reality (MR) as well as Diminished Reality (DR) and Modulated Reality (ModR), has emerged as a ground-breaking technology with the potential to reshape various aspects of our lives. From entertainment and education to healthcare and industry, XR applications are continually pushing the boundaries of what is possible, offering immersive and interactive experiences that were once the reserve of science fiction. As with any disruptive technology, however, the adoption of XR brings with it a range of challenges and concerns that must be carefully considered to maximize its benefits and minimize potential harm.

Our month 6 deliverable target was to report on our process for identifying and selecting use cases on good practices for XR technologies. Our medium-term goal is to employ a Delphi research methodology (a method for establishing consensus amongst experts through iterative surveys) to create a set of recommendations that will maximise the potential of this technology.

We have made an important step towards that goal in these first 6 months by developing an exploratory survey to understand the state-of-the-art in XR for user experience (from what makes a compelling experience to identifying barriers to access) and design practice. This survey has been administered to our networks to canvas the opinions of experts in XR technology. The responses from this survey will be used as a starting position to set bounds on the Delphi survey. The responses (reported below) are already allowing us to feed expert insights into other workstreams (e.g., WP4 and WP7) with immediate effect. In the longer term, the survey responses will help inform the development of a library of annotated real-world examples across different sectors later in WP6.

2 METHODOLOGY

We chose to implement an exploratory survey at this stage in the project so that we could rapidly acquire in-depth and nuanced responses from individuals with extensive knowledge of the field. Participants for the survey were selected through a purposive sampling method, which involved identifying and contacting individuals who were recognized as experts in the field of XR technologies.

The survey instrument was designed to collect data on experts' experiences and opinions on best practices in XR, as well as to identify use cases that could be considered as good practices in the field. The survey questions were developed based on reviews of existing research on XR technologies (Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Mourtzis et al., 2022) and their applications and through consultation with the WP6 consortium—all experts in this technology. The survey mainly comprised of open-ended questions to allow the experts to provide detailed and nuanced responses based on their experiences and expertise with XR technologies. Open-ended questions provide more flexibility and allow respondents to express their opinions and ideas in their own words, without being constrained by predefined response options. These questions were complemented by Likert scale questions used to capture the experts' ratings and perceptions of certain aspects of XR, such as accessibility and the importance of different factors in creating an effective XR experience.

Combining open-ended questions with Likert scales can provide a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' views, as open-ended questions provide rich qualitative data, while Likert scales provide a way to quantify the responses and compare them across different dimensions. In this survey, the open-ended questions allowed the experts to provide detailed insights into their experiences and opinions, while the Likert scales provided a way to quantify and compare their responses across different

dimensions, such as accessibility and the importance of different factors in creating an effective XR experience.

The survey was conducted online using the survey tool Qualtrics and participants were given until 30th March 2023 to complete the survey. We utilized the R programming language for the analysis of survey data. RStudio was used as the primary integrated development environment (IDE), and the “tidyverse” package (Wickham et al., 2019) was utilized for data manipulation, with ggplot2 (*Create Elegant Data Visualisations Using the Grammar of Graphics*, n.d.) for visualization. These tools allowed for efficient and reproducible analysis. For the open-ended responses, the data analysis process involved identifying themes and patterns in the experts' responses, as well as summarizing and categorizing their answers.

In addition to the quantitative survey analysis, we conducted a general review and summary of the open-ended responses. This approach allowed us to informally extract and summarize key themes and extracts from these responses for each open-ended item. We emphasize the importance of flexibility and selecting research methods appropriate to the context and goals of the study. Extracting themes in this informal manner allowed for a more nuanced understanding of the respondents' attitudes and opinions beyond the closed-ended survey questions in an efficient manner (Yanow & Schwartz-Shea, 2015).

This analysis is complemented by sentiment analysis on all open-ended response data using the R package “tidytext”. For this, we made use of the NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon (EmoLex), a well-established database containing over 14,000 English words and their associated scores for eight basic emotions (anger, fear, anticipation, trust, surprise, sadness, joy, and disgust). We used this Emotion classification approach to analyze the emotional content of the open-ended responses in our survey. This approach assigned each word a score for each of the eight basic emotions, as well as for valence and arousal, enabling us to quantitatively assess the emotional content of the text and identify latent themes and patterns in the open-ended data.

2.1 Survey Development & Dissemination

The partners within WP6 worked together to develop a list of questions that aligned with the overall goals of the project, work package and this specific deliverable. Through an iterative process involving group online meetings and asynchronous editing of an online document, the questions were refined. There was unanimous agreement that the majority of the survey should include free-text questions to allow participants to give detailed statements on the different topics. We also discussed the amount of demographic information to be retrieved. To fulfil GDPR requirements, an introductory page was prepared that explains the purpose of the questionnaire as well as several consent statements that needed to be agreed by the participant. After this process the content was transferred to Qualtrics, an online survey tool with a large set of functionalities and features.

In a pilot testing round, some questions were revisited and improved. By end of February 2023, the survey was published online. An information campaign was started to attract as many experts in XR as possible from across Europe to participate in this survey. All colleagues within XR4HUMAN distributed the survey to their individual network of experts. Thanks to our partner XR4Europe, the survey was also shared with the following clusters:

- Virtual Switzerland
- ImmersivaXR
- EDFVR
- Virtual Reality Berlin-Brandenburg
- FIVR
- Helsinki XR Center
- XR Hub Bavaria
- Innovate UK
- Immerse UK

2.2 Security, Ethics and Privacy

To protect the privacy and security of our survey respondents, we implemented several measures when creating the survey. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. All data collected were stored securely and protected from unauthorized access or breaches and we used the Qualtrics platform because it is fully compliant with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Measures were implemented to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of respondents, such as aggregating data and limiting access to survey results. Participants were informed that they were free to exit the window before submitting their answers. If they exited and did not save their answers, the responses would not be saved.

We did ask participants to leave their email address at the end of the survey if they would like to contribute to the subsequent Delphi study. This response column was stripped from the dataset prior to analysis and will only be used for the purpose of inviting participants to be involved in that follow-up research (the Delphi study).

Participants were provided with an email address (immersivetech[at]leeds.ac.uk) to contact the Centre for Immersive Technologies team if they had any questions about this project. The survey was approved by the School of Psychology Ethics Committee at the University of Leeds.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Participant Demographics

At the time of reporting 38 participants completed the survey. The majority of participants in this survey were male (66.7%) compared to females (33.3%), which likely reflects the demographics of those involved in XR and the technology sector more broadly. Most of the participants were researchers/scientist/ academics (70.8%) with only one other category (manager) including more than one participant. Within these occupations, 11 (45.8%) of them fell under independent research institutions and 4 (16.7%) fell within small/medium and university organisations.

In examining Nationality, we found that most participants were German (41.7%), followed by Dutch (8.3%), Spanish (8.3%), and British (8.3%). The range of participants also included Italian (4.2%), French (4.2%), South African (4.2%), Pakistani (4.2%), Greek (4.2%), and Norwegian (4.2%). Similarly, most participants currently live in Germany (41.7%), with the second highest majority living in the Netherlands (16.7%) and Norway (16.7%). Participants were also asked to state their ethnicity. From the 29.2% of participants that responded to this question, 42.9% identified as White.

Most participants expressed that they had an extensive amount of experience with over 66.7% of participants having over 5 years' experience with XR technologies overall responses ranged from 1-28 years (Mean = 8.5 years). Only 3 participants claimed to have little experience with XR technology. From those respondents, 2 stated that they had a year of experience with XR, and the other participant stated that they had 10 years of experience.

We asked participants what type of XR technology they were most familiar with. VR headsets (87.5%), Unity3D (70.9%), AR glasses (50%) and desktop VR (62.5%) were used by over half the participants with the majority using VR headsets and Unity3D. Less than a quarter of participants used the following devices/tools/platforms: Google ARCore (20.8%), Apple ARKit, VR chat (20.8%) and Recroom (25%).

The majority stated that they use these technologies for education and research purposes (58.3%) with the second most common application being Social VR (37.5%) and Industry 4.0 (37.5%). One

participant expressed that they used the technology for “Journalism and Weather”. Commonly the majority (80%) of participants who selected other (20.8%) described use of the technologies of entertainment and media purposes.

3.2 Perspectives on Accessibility

We asked participants to rate the degree of accessibility (on a 5-point Likert scale going from Very Inaccessible to Very Accessible) of current XR technologies for a range of demographics. We chose not to provide a specific definition for accessibility to encourage participants to respond based on their own understanding and interpretation of the term. This approach aligns with the exploratory nature of our study, as it allows us to capture a diverse range of perspectives and experiences related to accessibility. Defining accessibility upfront could potentially constrain participants' responses by limiting their focus to the provided definition. By allowing participants to interpret the term themselves, we aimed to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how accessibility is perceived in different contexts and by different individuals. This approach also helps us identify any common themes or misconceptions that may emerge from the open-ended responses, which can be useful in informing future research.

The categorical responses were converted to numerical values ranging from -2 to +2 and mean and standard error values were computed to quantify the accessibility rating for each demographic. A full profile of responses, with demographics ranked in order of accessibility is shown in [Figure 1](#).

Experts rated that individuals with vision loss would have the lowest accessibility rating with a mean of -1.923 (SE = 0.077). Depth perception issues with a mean of -1.300 (SE = 0.260) were the second least accessible.

Responses indicate that participants with cognitive impairments rated the accessibility of XR technologies as relatively low, with a mean rating of -1.133 (SE = 0.236). Similarly, individuals with colour vision deficiency also reported a lower degree of accessibility with a mean rating of -0.750 (SE = 0.279). Participants with little education and older adults were reported to have negative accessibility ratings, with means of -0.467 (SE = 0.322) and -0.529 (SE = 0.259), respectively. Those with low digital literacy also ranked low, with a mean of -1.188 (SE = 0.188). Physical impairments were also associated with lower accessibility ratings, with a mean of -0.867 (SE = 0.215). Lastly, young children had a mean accessibility rating of -0.588 (SE = 0.272).

In contrast, corrected-to-normal vision individuals reported a neutral accessibility rating with a mean of 0.000 (SE = 0.257). Notably, females and middle-aged adults reported positive accessibility ratings, with means of 0.812 (SE = 0.306) and 0.765 (SE = 0.265), respectively. Similarly, male participants and teenagers reported relatively high accessibility ratings, with means of 1.467 (SE = 0.192) and 1.176 (SE = 0.196), respectively. Young adults reported the highest accessibility rating with a mean of 1.824 (SE = 0.095).

Figure 1: Expert Ratings on the degree of accessibility of current XR technologies for range of demographics. Black dots show mean accessibility ratings and error bars show +/- 1SEM. Individual data points are jittered for purposes of illustration.

3.3 User-friendliness of Current XR

In the next set of questions to elaborate on the state-of-art, we asked participants to rate the extent to which current XR technologies can deliver positive experiences. We also asked experts how frequently they encountered difficulties when using XR and/or navigating through XR experiences (**Figure 2**). Most participants rated the ability to deliver positive experiences as good (18%) or fair (15%). Surprisingly, given the experience of our participants with XR, the majority of participants stated that they experienced difficulties in using XR about half the time and (18%) sometimes. None of the participants indicated that they never experienced difficulties.

Figure 2: (A) Participants were asked to rate the ability of current XR technologies to deliver positive user experiences; (B) the degree to which our experts encountered difficulties in using and/or navigating through XR experiences.

3.4 Usability & User Experience Considerations

We asked participants: What are the most important usability and user experience (UX) considerations for XR?

Although the present material is limited in numbers, and contains a span in user experience, one may assume that there is a certain representability in the material. What constitutes the most important usability and UX for XR are the following, although not necessarily in this sequence:

- Logical and intuitive log-on
- Adequate resolution on video and sound (HD quality preferably)
- Integration between software and hardware, i.e., unified interfaces
- Eliminating cyber-sickness / motion sickness
- Emphasis on “ease of use”

One of the primary themes identified by the experts was the importance of a logical and intuitive log-on process. Users should be able to access XR experiences seamlessly, without encountering confusing or overly complicated authentication steps. An effortless log-on experience sets the tone for the rest of the user journey, helping to ensure that users remain engaged and receptive to the XR environment.

Another vital aspect highlighted by the participants was the need for adequate resolution in both video and sound, with a strong preference for high-definition (HD) quality. This level of fidelity is crucial for creating immersive and convincing XR experiences, as it enables users to feel truly present in the virtual environment. High-quality audio and visual components contribute to a more engaging and enjoyable user experience, which in turn can increase adoption and satisfaction rates.

The integration of software and hardware was also cited as a significant factor in XR usability and user experience. Unified interfaces are crucial for streamlining interactions and minimizing potential

frustration for users. By ensuring that software and hardware components work together seamlessly, developers can create more cohesive and user-friendly XR experiences.

Cyber-sickness and motion sickness emerged as common concerns in the survey. To enhance user experience and ensure the comfort of all participants, XR developers must prioritize the elimination of these issues. By incorporating techniques such as adjusting frame rates, optimizing field of view, and improving head-tracking accuracy, XR experiences can become more accessible and enjoyable for a broader range of users. Users report that a satisfactory UX is highly connected to a smooth interface. It seems that these aspects, although listed as independent by the respondents, should be perceived as interdependent.

An intriguing aspect often observed in the realm of training and education software is the repurposing of platforms for applications they were not originally designed to accommodate. Notable instances include the incorporation of Facebook and other social media channels into teaching and learning environments. It's worth mentioning that Learning Management Systems inherently possess elements of governance, control, and administration. Consequently, one of the survey respondents emphasized the necessity of engaging educators and teachers in the development process of XR technologies intended for educational applications. By doing so, developers can ensure that learning theories and appropriate design principles are thoughtfully integrated, ultimately leading to more effective and pedagogically sound XR experiences.

Lastly, the experts emphasized the importance of "ease of use" as a fundamental aspect of XR usability and user experience. To foster widespread adoption, XR technologies must be designed with user-centric principles, ensuring that even individuals with limited technical expertise can navigate and engage with these immersive environments effortlessly. By focusing on simplicity and intuitiveness, XR developers can create experiences that resonate with a diverse array of users and encourage widespread adoption of these transformative technologies.

3.5 Key Factors Underlying Positive User Experience

We asked participants: What are the key factors that contribute to a positive XR user experience?

Most respondents highlighted sense of immersion, a comfortable experience for the user, intuitive and responsive interaction, and high system performance as key factors. Some highlighted good storytelling, a compelling use-case, and that the XR application should offer something different to other media in a useful way. One of the respondents commented on achieving a balance between expectation, management, and surprise. In other words, that users have a sense of what to expect and accept system limitations, but that the experience nevertheless goes beyond their expectations by offering pleasant surprises.

Where respondents disagree is on whether a highly realistic representation of 3D content, including scenes and humans, is important. While a small minority of respondents expressed that highly realistic representation is a key factor, more respondents commented that it was important to focus on the user experience being comfortable and on avoiding users getting frustrated with the user interface, as well as to focus on the quality of storytelling and gameplay. There should be a good match between visualisation, interaction, and task.

Specific issues that were listed as important to address in creating a positive XR experience include locomotion comfort, audio and visual information matching, optimised 3D environment to ensure high framerate. Other factors mentioned include tactile interactions, originality, fluidity in moving into and out of XR, and that the overall quality of the experience is sufficiently high as to not deter from the immersive experience.

It is interesting to note that only one respondent highlighted achieving a sense of *presence* as a key factor, while about half mentioned *immersion* as key. Perhaps this is because achieving presence is usually the goal of an XR experience rather than the key factor for achieving it?

Research indicates that sense of presence is less dependent of high visual or audio fidelity but more on the believability of the systems response to user interaction (Mania et al., 2006) – that the system behaves as anticipated so that the user accepts it as real. The behaviour can be highly realistic (e.g., for a training simulator) but can also bend the laws of physics as long as it is done in a consistent manner that meets the user's expectations. The same can apply to user interaction, where consistency and ease of use is arguably more important than naturalism (Bowman et al., 2012). Key to this is the user achieving a suspension of disbelief in the experience. For example, a cartoon animation can trigger a strong emotional response and a viewer can learn from a cartoon even though the rendering and animation is clearly not visually realistic (Lasseter, 1987). When done well, the user accepts the experience as “real” and engages with the story. Related to this is the uncanny valley effect, where the user struggles to suspend disbelief because the rendering is so realistic that the user reacts negatively to the slightest deviations detected that are against expectations. However, it should be noted that high visual quality is significant for training tasks that focus on visual scanning in complex environments, so for *some* XR experience then high visual quality is certainly important (Ragan et al., n.d.).

3.5.1 Positive User Experience Examples

We further probed participants on the question of positive user experiences, inviting them to highlight examples of such factors in practice. The survey participants provided several examples of XR applications that showcase positive user experiences, and these applications cover a wide range of genres and platforms. By examining these examples, we can gain a better understanding of what makes these experiences successful and engaging.

Horizon Call of the Mountain on PlayStation VR is a noteworthy recent example of a visually impressive and immersive VR game. This title offers players an engaging narrative and an expansive virtual world to explore, resulting in a captivating experience that truly transports users into the game's universe.

For new users, the Oculus Quest and SteamVR (The Lab) tutorials, as well as Tilt Brush, present valuable lessons on how to navigate and interact with the VR environment. These tutorials are designed to be user-friendly and engaging, ensuring that even novice users can quickly become comfortable with the technology.

Popular games like Beat Saber and Super-Hot integrate movement mechanics as a core aspect of the gameplay. In Beat Saber, for instance, the simplicity of its visuals is complemented by the integration of music, creating an engaging experience that appeals to a wide range of users. These games demonstrate how natural and intuitive interactions can enhance user enjoyment and immersion.

Fruit Ninja VR is another game that showcases seamless integration of interaction mechanics. The process of selecting menu options involves the same interaction as the game itself—cutting fruit with swords. This consistency between the user interface and gameplay creates a cohesive and enjoyable experience.

Half-Life: Alyx was noted a prime example of a VR game that allows users to interact with most objects in a way that feels physically and logically accurate. A respondent noted that the level of interactivity and realism helps to create a truly immersive and convincing virtual environment.

In addition to these specific XR applications, participants also mentioned scenarios that are particularly well-suited for positive XR user experiences. For instance, digital testimonies of Holocaust survivors in VR can evoke powerful emotions and memories by bridging the past and present. Another example is XR-enabled virtual meetings with real-time volumetric human representation, where users can

experience a sense of presence and connection. However, it is crucial to achieve a certain level of audio-visual fidelity in order to elicit positive responses from users in such scenarios.

These examples and scenarios highlight the importance of intuitive interactions, engaging content, and immersive environments in delivering positive user experiences in the realm of XR technologies.

3.6 Key Factors Contributing to Poor UX

The survey also delved into the key factors that contribute to poor user experiences in XR applications, covering a wide range of aspects that are critical to the design process. These core elements pertain to all user experience approaches within XR and are independent of the output device, ranging from handheld devices primarily used for Augmented Reality (AR) to standalone Virtual Reality (VR) experiences. We cover 7 themes in an elaboration of the analysis below: (a) Comfort and safety; (b) Interaction (affordance, signifiers, feedback); (c) Environment and spatial components; (d) Sensory input (visual, audio, haptics); (e) Engagement (storytelling, gamification); (f) Constraints; (g) Inclusion, diversity, and accessibility.

a) Comfort and Safety

Throughout the evolution of XR technologies, comfort and safety have been significant concerns and continue to be essential aspects of UX design. Despite advancements in head-mounted displays (HMDs), comfort issues persist and can lead to user rejection. Safety concerns, including user movement and maintaining appropriate distances while wearing headsets, should not be underestimated. The web is full of historic video and images of this technology causing injuries and damages resulting from poorly executed VR sessions. Ensuring user awareness, providing guidance, and emphasizing user onboarding can help address XR safety concerns, ultimately keeping users safe and comfortable.

b) Interaction

A critical aspect of XR design is communicating how users should interact with objects. UX designers should consider questions like:

- Is an item usable?
- How do I use it?
- Am I doing the right thing?
- How do I get from point A to point B?
- What locomotion options do I have?

Designers can draw inspiration from Don Norman's "The Design of Everyday Things," which discusses affordances and signifiers to clarify object functionality. Affordances refer to the potential actions or uses that a user perceives in an object or system based on its physical or digital properties. For example, a door handle affords pulling or pushing to open the door, while a button affords pressing to activate a function. Affordances can be visual, tactile, or auditory. Signifiers, on the other hand, are indicators or cues that communicate the possible actions or uses of an object or system to the user. They can be visual, auditory, or tactile, and they can be explicit or implicit. For example, a signifier of a button's function could be a label or an icon that indicates what the button does, or it could be the shape and texture of the button itself that suggests its purpose.

c) Environment and Spatial Components

In AR, environments and spatial components are crucial, as data and digital content are integrated with and interact with the physical surroundings. In VR, the environment holds equal importance, but its role in UX design is distinct. Designers must consider factors such as seated vs. standing contexts and application orientations. The virtual environment is the primary driver of user experience, with spatial

design decisions shaping the story-living experience. Story-living is a vital component, particularly in non-linear approaches, as users explore spaces through directional actions.

d) Sensory input

Sensory input options offer a rich array of tools to direct, orchestrate, and guide users' experiences in XR through visual cues, spatial audio navigation, and haptic feedback. For example, spatial audio can guide users' attention and navigation towards specific areas, while peripheral sound design can aid navigation through auditory cues. Visual feedback based on gaze, such as highlighted objects or selection rays, can assist users in completing tasks. Haptic controller feedback, often delivered through vibration, can prompt user action in response to specific events.

Interactive sensory input is a prominent aspect of UX design, but the underlying visual design structure also plays a vital role. This structure encompasses fundamental audio-visual communication concepts, design systems, and style decisions that influence the overall user experience.

e) Engagement

Successful UX design results in persistent user engagement by guiding users, reducing friction, offering incentives, and facilitating satisfying, purposeful, and meaningful experiences. This is achieved through continuous testing, prototyping during production, and considering all spatial and sensory components. Story-living and gamification are key elements to accomplishing this objective, providing direction and goals for users.

First-time XR users often ask questions such as:

- What am I supposed to do?
- Am I facing the right way?
- What should I do next?
- Is the task or action completed?

Effective user experience design is essential for engaging users in XR experiences, as they can often feel disoriented, confused, or uncertain about the experience's objectives. This may be due to a lack of familiarity with the technology. Addressing these issues involves monitoring user engagement during prototyping and testing, as well as refining story-living and gamification components based on user feedback and results.

e) Constraints

The core principle in XR experiences is to manage users' options, limit unnecessary or harmful actions, and provide support through discoverability and feedback. A prominent example is the guardian area, which users must set up individually to match their physical space, ensuring safe VR experiences. Conventional methods for restricting users' movements include visual cues to prevent damage and harm. Other constraint techniques involve fenced-off terrains, axis restrictions on objects, and using the field of view limits to direct attention. By disabling specific locomotion abilities, restricting access to areas, and limiting object interactions, constraints enable UX designers to guide users.

Designing location-based AR experiences requires a unique UX approach tailored to each specific location, such as escalators, benches, or roads. It is essential to account for potential risk points during both the conceptualization phase and the user journey, ensuring a purposeful and interactive location-based experience. The AR experience must seamlessly blend with and respond to its surroundings (e.g., Pokémon Go death list).

f) Inclusion, Diversity, and Accessibility

Inclusion, diversity, and accessibility hold significant importance for users in XR experiences. Designers should take into account the user's context, situation, physical and mental abilities, cultural and ethnic background, and the sociological impact of the design. For instance, promoting diversity can be achieved through engaging programming that counterbalances stereotypes or fosters inclusion by

offering a range of input device options within XR experiences, such as one-handed controllers, gesture controls, and vision controls.

3.6.1 Examples of Poor UX

Several respondents highlighted issues with various XR devices, such as the limited field of view of the HoloLens or challenges with haptic gloves, which can be cumbersome to put on and remove. In general, current devices may not provide an optimal fit, as mentioned by one respondent.

Regarding content, many social VR tools represent users in a cartoonish manner through simplistic avatars. One participant criticized the inability to interact with objects that seemingly invite interaction, as this immediately shatters the illusion.

Additionally, some participants reported experiencing motion sickness, latency, and delays in certain XR experiences, further contributing to suboptimal user experiences.

3.7 Industries & Use-Cases where XR is well-suited

We asked: “Are there any industries or specific use cases where you believe XR technology is well-suited?”

Education and training were identified by the majority of participants as sectors ideally suited for XR technology, closely followed by entertainment. Industrial training, for example, can greatly benefit from XR, as it enables hands-on tasks to be learned in a safe, controlled environment. Moreover, XR applications are valuable for live maintenance and monitoring tasks across various industries. The impressive visualization capabilities of XR for depicting true-scale designs can also benefit architecture, construction, and design industries.

For education, XR applications can help visualize abstract concepts, making them more understandable and fostering constructivist and experiential learning approaches. The same experiential learning capabilities can be applied to immersive storytelling. Specific industries mentioned also included healthcare and fitness.

Entertainment, particularly gaming and films, was another crucial use case noted by participants. Heritage and tourism were also highlighted as key areas for XR application. There was a consensus among participants that the potential applications for XR are vast; however, it is crucial to deploy the technology with a clear purpose and ensure intuitive, user-friendly interactions.

3.8 Industries & Use-Cases where XR is not suited

Next, we inquired about industries or specific use cases where participants believed XR technology might not be well-suited. The responses were divided equally between those who didn't see any unsuitable industries or use cases and those who provided examples of industries or use cases where XR might not be well-suited or could have limitations.

Careful design and adaptation are essential when creating computer-generated worlds for specific use cases. For instance, navigation systems in XR should be minimal to avoid distracting drivers. Industries considered less suitable for XR include data-sensitive domains such as healthcare and software development. One participant highlighted industries requiring close awareness and interaction with the physical environment, while another mentioned advertising industries that could overwhelm users with distracting information and extract sensitive user data, posing potential risks to XR users.

Specific use cases where XR might not be well-suited include childcare and working on a computer, as using XR head-mounted displays for extended periods can be uncomfortable.

3.9 Degree of Importance

Participants were asked to rank order a list of variables that the WP6 had generated as potentially important factors to consider in the design of XR for optimising the user experience. The rank ordered responses, from most important to least important, are presented in **Figure 3**.

The lower emphasis on achieving a high level of realism compared to the degree of immersion and interactivity aligns well with existing scientific literature on fidelity. Fidelity refers to the extent to which a computer device can replicate a real-world environment or how authentic the visualized experience appears and feels. Fidelity is categorized into visual (graphic) and functional fidelity.

Currently, significant resources are dedicated to making virtual experiences look as realistic as possible, based on the assumption that increased realism will lead to a better experience, as per the theory of identical elements. However, numerous fidelity studies have debunked this notion, demonstrating that functional fidelity (the degree of interactivity and the feeling of presence) is more critical than visual fidelity.

This is particularly true in education and training, where, beyond a certain threshold, additional visual fidelity can in fact hinder the learning process^{28/04/2023 18:02:00} (Alessi, 1988). This is due to the increased cognitive load imposed by the visual richness of the medium, which can overwhelm learners. Consequently, it is essential to prioritize functional fidelity and immersive interactivity to create more effective and engaging XR experiences, rather than solely focusing on visual realism.

Figure 3: Ranking of importance of different features for delivering a good user experience in XR. Note that Other Response rated as most important by one respondent was: “Consistency of the presented virtual environment”.

Almost half of the meaningful words contained emotions of "Trust" and "Anticipation," suggesting that they are both significant features of the current discussions on user experience and design considerations for XR. It is important to note that "Trust" can have both positive and negative connotations in this context. On the one hand, trust might indicate confidence and reliability in the technology and its potential. On the other hand, it might also represent concerns about the trustworthiness of the technology or the entities behind it, such as data privacy issues or potential misuse.

Similarly, "Anticipation" can be viewed as a double-edged sword. While it may signify excitement and eagerness for future developments in XR, it could also imply anxiety and uncertainty about the direction the technology is heading.

The prominence of these emotions in the discussions highlights the importance of understanding the nuances of trust and anticipation in relation to XR technology. To ensure continued adoption and development of XR, designers and developers must address potential concerns and strike a balance between creating engaging, forward-looking experiences and maintaining transparency, ethical practices, and a secure environment for users.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This report summarises the results of an exploratory survey designed to understand the factors that contribute to good XR user experiences & practices. This was the major foundational piece of work for WP6, enabling us to rapidly acquire insights from experts in the community on the current state of art. A total of 38 responses were evaluated, and since the majority of our questions involved free-text answers, careful synthesis and extraction of the main messages were necessary.

The major findings can be summarized as follows:

- The expert ratings on the degree of accessibility of current XR technologies indicated that individuals without any impairments, physical or mental deficiencies—regardless of gender or age—have the best accessibility to XR technologies. Notably, our experts suggested that current XR was only accessible to approximately half of society— a critical issue that must be investigated more deeply and addressed if this sector is to fulfil its potential.
- A good user experience depends on a harmonious balance between visualization, interaction, and task.
- Usability of interfaces and headsets remains a challenge.
- A sense of immersion was identified as the most crucial factor for a positive XR experience.
- Conversely, various factors contribute to a poor XR experience, including comfort and safety, interaction, environment and spatial components, sensory input, engagement, and inclusion.
- Education and training emerged as sectors well-suited for XR technology, followed by entertainment. XR is also beneficial for industrial training and live maintenance and monitoring tasks across various industries.
- On other hand, our experts suggested that XR is not well-suited in data sensitive domains until issues of privacy can be addressed. Activities that require using HMDs for long periods of time were also considered unsuitable given the size of current headsets, but this could be resolved in the longer term through increasing miniaturisation of hardware and optimisation. Childcare was highlighted a specific example where XR might never be appropriate.
- Finally, the experts were asked to rank the importance factors and degree of immersion, degree of presence and degree of interactivity was ranked highest.

Overall, the findings from this exploratory survey demonstrate the potential of XR technologies across a range of sectors, including education, training, entertainment, and industry. However, several challenges and limitations still need to be addressed to ensure the effective implementation of XR applications, particularly in terms of accessibility and usability.

The results of this analysis will serve as a foundation for other work packages and guide subsequent activities in WP6. The Delphi study that follows will provide an opportunity to consult with expert respondents and reach a consensus on best practices in XR development and implementation. The library of experiences planned for the online platform (T6.3) and demonstrator sites across Europe can showcase the potential of XR technologies and inspire further innovation and collaboration across different sectors.

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